

Magnesium Foliar Application and Phosphorien Soil Inoculation Positively Affect *Pisum sativum* L. Plants Grown on Sandy Calcareous Soil

Authors : Saad M. Howladar, Ashraf Sh. Osman, Mostafa M. Rady, Hassan S. Al-Zahrani

Abstract : The effects of soil inoculation with phosphorien-containing Phosphate-Dissolving Bacteria (PDB) and/or magnesium (Mg) foliar application at the rates of 0, 0.5 and 1mM on growth, green pod and seed yields, and chemical constituents of *Pisum sativum* L. grown on a sandy calcareous soil were investigated. Results indicated that PDB and/or Mg significantly increased shoot length, number of branches plant⁻¹, total leaf area plant⁻¹ and canopy dry weight plant⁻¹, leaf contents of pigments, soluble sugars, free proline, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, magnesium, and calcium, and Ca/Na ratio, while leaf Na content was reduced. PDB and/or Mg also increased green pod and seed yields. We concluded that PDB and Mg have pronounced positive effects on *Pisum sativum* L. plants grown on sandy calcareous soil. PDB and Mg, therefore, have the potential to be applied for various crops to overcome the adverse effects of the newly-reclaimed sandy calcareous soils.

Keywords : bio-p-fertilizer, mg foliar application, newly-reclaimed soils, *Pisum sativum* L.

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